

Tools developed by ICT4Water Cluster partners — Preliminary Survey

Prepared by: ICT4Water Actor Engagement & Co-creation Group

Intro

The Actor Engagement and Co-creation Group of the ICT4Water Cluster is embarking on a comprehensive research initiative to understand and document the tools (digital tools, stakeholder engagement, and citizen science) developed or utilized by projects that are or were partners in the Cluster. Our aim is to compile a holistic inventory of these tools and measure various aspects of them, from their functionality and interoperability to their impact and potential for scalability.

This will culminate in a scientific publication to support future projects and stakeholders in the digital-water domain.

Thank you for your contribution.

An asterisk () indicates a required question. **

Section A — Project metadata

1. **Project Name***
2. **Link of the website***
3. **Start Date***
4. **End Date***
5. **Brief Description of the project ***

Section B — Step 1

6. **Did your project develop or utilize one of the following? ***
 - a) Digital Tool (Virtual reality, Augmented reality or Mixed reality)
 - b) Stakeholders Engagement (Living Labs, Community of Practices, Multistakeholder Forum, System Innovation Approach etc.)
 - c) Citizens Science

If you answered Yes for Digital Tool (VR/AR/MR)

7. **Did your project develop or utilize digital tools? *** (Yes/No)
8. **Type of digital tool/tools** (select all that apply):
 - Virtual reality
 - Augmented reality
 - Mixed reality
9. **Name of the digital tool/tools**
10. **Name and email of responsible person to be contacted***
11. **Brief description of the tool/tools**

If you answered Yes for Stakeholders Engagement

11. **Did your project develop or utilize any type of stakeholders' engagement tool? *** (Yes/No)
12. **Name and/or type of stakeholders' engagement***
13. **Type of stakeholders' engagement (if known)** (select all that apply):
 - Living Labs
 - Community of Practices
 - Multistakeholder Forum
 - System Innovation Approach
 - Other: _____
14. **Brief description**
15. **Name and email of responsible person to be contacted***

If you answered Yes for Citizens Science

16. **Did your project develop or utilize any citizens science tool? *** (Yes/No)
17. **Name of the tool***
18. **Brief description**
19. **Name and email of responsible person to be contacted***

Section C — Final

20. **Is there anything else you would like to state or recommend?**

Thank you for your contribution.